

3 Poems by Dr Barbaros İrdelmen

English translation by Huri ÖZDOĞAN

Belle's Dance

As the belle spun on the floor
Drunken applause
Was cracking the chest of the bar
Sweaty gazes,
Bodies gone mad with lust
Beers ice-cold
The minds are scattered.
She was the belle of the age
She knew her job well
What she earned
No one could ever calculate
She commanded the peoples:
You will buy fighter jets from me.
You, your land
And you, your oil
You will give them to me
Otherwise
My smile will come down on your faces
Like a slap
I will beat you all...

How much does it cost?

I asked in the abstract market
For a smile
You cannot find, they said
It's not a season for it
Is there a laughter?
No way, it is too unavailable
Who lost it
So that you can find it
How much does love cost?
Its lifespan is short
It's so perishable, for a long while
We don't put them on the counter
What do we have in this season?
Ass-kissing, flattery
Lies, slander, fraudulency
Insult, curse, disdain
All of them are both fresh and easy
Abundant in four seasons

If it's dark

We parted suddenly, my love
My mind is on you
Are you alone?
Are you unhappy?
Do you miss me?
What do you want from the world beyond?
Just whisper
If it's warm,
Wind, coolness, rain
If you're cold, the sun
If the nights are dark,
A bright moonlight
Whatever you want
From the other world
I can send it right away

Bio:

Barbaros İrdelmen, poet, writer, translator, and retired specialist in internal medicine and nephrology with 19 published poetry collections to date, his works have been included in numerous national and international anthologies and poetry festivals. Currently a poetry columnist for Edebiyat Magazin Newspaper and TV also contributes actively to prominent literary journals such as Pazartesi14 NEYYA Edebiyat, Kirpi Edebiyat ve Düşünce Dergisi, writer for the Papirus Magazine, Literature House, Our Poetry Archive, Atunis Galaxy Poetry writer. As a member of the Writers Syndicate of Turkey, he is also as a leading figure in the translation of world poetry written in English.